

Pulse-to-pulse wavelength switching of a nanosecond fiber laser by four-wave mixing seeded stimulated Raman amplification

MATTHIAS EIBL^{1,†}, SEBASTIAN KARPFF^{2,†}, HUBERTUS HAKERT¹, TORBEN BLÖMKER¹,
JAN PHILIP KOLB¹, CHRISTIAN JIRAUSCHEK³, AND ROBERT HUBER^{1,*}

¹Institut für Biomedizinische Optik, Universität zu Lübeck, Lübeck, Peter-Monnik-Weg 4, 23562 Lübeck, Germany

²Department of Electrical Engineering, University of California, Los Angeles, California 90095, USA

³Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Technical University of Munich (TUM), Arcisstr. 21, D-80333 Munich, Germany

*robert.huber@bmo.uni-luebeck.de

[†]These authors contributed equally to this Letter.

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We report on a multi-color fiber laser based on four-wave mixing (FWM) and stimulated Raman scattering (SRS), delivering rapidly wavelength switchable narrowband output at 1064 nm, 1122 nm, and 1186 nm. High power pulses from a nanosecond pulsed fiber master oscillator power amplifier (MOPA) at 1064 nm are combined with 1122 nm seed light for Raman amplification at the 1st Stokes order in a standard single mode fiber. With increasing power we observe a narrowband spectral component at 1186 nm, without any additional seed or resonator at this wavelength. We analyze this occurrence of a narrowband 2nd Stokes order both experimentally and theoretically and suggest it is a result of FWM seeding the SRS amplification in the fiber. We demonstrate that the wavelength shifting can be controlled electronically within microseconds for very rapid and even pulse-to-pulse wavelength changes. This wavelength conversion method can extend the spectral coverage of single wavelength fiber lasers for biomedical imaging. © 2017 Optical Society of America

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High power fiber lasers with single mode fiber output are an attractive choice for many fields of research where high beam quality and flexible beam delivery is required. Actively modulated fiber based master oscillator power amplifiers (MOPA) fulfill these requirements and yield additional advantages like power scalability, variable pulse width and variable repetition rate. However, the amplifiers are spectrally limited to the rather

narrowband fiber-based gain media currently available. The two most prominent dopants for fiber amplifiers – ytterbium (Yb) and erbium (Er) – roughly cover a range from 1020 nm to 1100 nm and from 1500 nm to 1600 nm, respectively. The region in-between these ranges would be highly interesting for biomedical imaging as it would provide a higher penetration depth but it lacks a proper gain medium [1-4].

Therefore, various approaches have been proposed to convert the output power from fiber gain regions from 1100 nm to 1500 nm. One way to achieve this is to use stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) in the fiber itself [5, 6]. This is either achieved with a Raman laser, where a resonator is built for one or more wavelengths [7], or with a single pass Raman amplifier where a seed signal is amplified by simulated Raman scattering through an intense pump [8]. Also a combination of both concepts has been shown [9].

Another approach is to use four-wave mixing (FWM) as wavelength shifting mechanism. For efficient FWM interaction, the involved wavelengths have to be phase matched, which can be achieved by specially designed fibers [10]. As these fibers can be quite expensive and are not easy to handle, wavelength conversion in standard single mode fiber (SMF) would be desired. However, in the normal dispersion regime of SMF the phase matching requirement cannot be fulfilled and efficient conversion with FWM is not possible [11, 12].

The combination of both effects, Raman and FWM, however, can yield the desired result. This has been studied in literature as Raman assisted FWM [13]. This combination has tremendous potential as FWM can provide narrowband operation and SRS provides high gain with low noise characteristics without the need for phase matching. However, the generation of spectrally narrowband higher order cascaded output has not been investigated so far.

In this paper, we report on a highly efficient cascaded Raman laser output at 1186 nm with a linewidth below 70 pm. We analyze the contributing factors of FWM and SRS and thus suggest that FWM provides the narrowband seed and SRS the high gain. In our model, the Raman gain breaks the periodic generation and annihilation of FWM photons and an efficient amplification within the Raman gain bandwidth is achieved. We thus call it FWM seeded SRS. This model is further supported by numerical simulations which confirm the experimental observations. We show that electronically switching in a pulse-to-pulse manner between the three wavelengths 1064 nm, 1122 nm, and 1186 nm is possible due to the instantaneous response of FWM and SRS.

Fig. 1. Basic scheme of the laser with measurement setup: The modulated and amplified output of a 1064 nm laser diode is converted to a multispectral output by FWM assisted SRS in passive fiber. EOM: electro-optical-modulator, YDFA: ytterbium doped fiber amplifier, PD: photo diode, PM: thermal power meter, OSA: optical spectrum analyzer, S: beam sampler, WDM: wavelength division multiplexer, PG: pulse generator; BS: 3 dB beam splitter.

The basic setup is depicted in figure 1. We pump a standard single mode fiber with high power 1064 nm pulses from a fiber MOPA and seed the 1st Raman-Stokes order at 1122 nm (cf. fig. 1 and fig. 4). Through the non-linear interaction of the different light fields, light at 1186 nm is generated without any additional components.

The master oscillator signal is provided by a spectrally narrowband 1064 nm laser diode (LD, Lumics, LU1064M300) with a close-to-chip fiber-bragg grating (FBG). Its output is actively modulated by an electro-optical-modulator with a 3 dB bandwidth of 12 GHz (EOM, Phottline, NIR-MX-LN 10) to adjustable 50 ps - 5 ns pulses. Electronic pulses to drive the EOM are provided by a fast pulse generator (PG, AlnairLabs EPG-210 or Wavepond DAX14000). As the EOM has a limited extinction ratio of ~ 30 dB, leaking continuous wave (CW) light would deplete the following YDFAs. We thus pre-modulate the seed laser diode to 20 ns pulses to further enhance the light extinction in between the pulses. The close-to-chip FBG ensures enough feedback round-trips for stable and narrowband lasing operation. After the EOM, the seed pulses have an optical peak power of ~ 100 mW which get amplified in a three stage ytterbium doped fiber amplifier (YDFA) up to kW of peak power. Each of the first two YDFAs consists of ~ 1 m core pumped ytterbium doped fiber (Nufern, SM-YSF-HI). The 976 nm pump light (Lumics, LU0975M500) is coupled into the YDF in backward direction with a fused wavelength division multiplexer (WDM). An isolator before the YDF protects components from backward going amplified stimulated emission (ASE) and a 3 nm fiber band-pass filter removes ASE in forward direction (all fiber components purchased from Advanced Fiber Resources). The third amplification stage is made of ~ 4 m double clad (DC) ytterbium fiber (Nufern, LMA-YDF-10/125-9M) pumped in

forward direction by a single multi-mode pump diode (Lumics, LU0975T090). We spliced a combination of 2 m SMF28 and 2 m Hi1060 (both Corning) directly on the DC-YDFA as passive fiber for Raman scattering. Before the DC-YDFA, a 1064 nm/1122 nm WDM is installed to insert the 1122 nm Raman seed laser. This seed laser is also pre-modulated to 40 ns pulses with a peak power of ~ 100 mW to circumvent depletion of the last amplifier stage. Inserting the Raman seed light before the last amplification stage has two important advantages. First, having the Raman seed present as early as possible effectively suppresses the broadband spontaneous Raman background that would arise as soon as the power within the YDFA reaches the Raman threshold. Second, it lowers the power exposure to the WDM and thus prevents possible damage to this component.

The wavelength shifter is based on the Raman gain of the delivery fiber which is spliced onto the forward pumped DC-YDFA. The combination of 2 m SMF28 and 2 m Hi1060 was chosen by cut-back method for optimal performance. Even though SMF28 has a cutoff wavelength of 1250 nm, we observe single mode operation below this cutoff wavelength if all connections are fusion spliced [14]. Fused silica has a broad Raman gain maximum for a frequency shift of 13 THz to 15 THz [6]. The seed wavelength of 1122 nm, representing 14.5 THz from 1064 nm, was chosen to maximize both the wavelength shift and the Raman gain at the same time.

For the following measurements, the pulse length was set to 1 ns and the repetition rate to 50 kHz. This results in a duty cycle of 5×10^5 or a factor of 20,000 from cw-power to peak power. It should be mentioned that the pulse length can be set roughly within a range of ~ 30 ps to 2 ns with the same outcome. The lower boundary is given by the onset of self-phase modulation (SPM) or cross-phase modulation (XPM) and the higher boundary by upcoming stimulated Brillouin scattering (SBS). The main power limitation in our pulse length regime is SRS and FWM [12]. The repetition rate could be increased up to several MHz. Here, the pump power and the fiber damage threshold are currently the limitations in our setup.

The pulses are coupled out from the fiber amplifier and analyzed with a 500 MHz photo-diode (PD, Fermionics, FD300), a thermal power meter (PM, Thorlabs, S470C), and an optical spectrum analyzer (OSA, Yokogawa, AQ6370) (cf. fig. 1, right). A beam sampler (S, Thorlabs, BSF10-C) and a broadband 50:50 beam splitter (BS, Thorlabs, BS015) are used to split the beam into the different ports.

Before implementing rapid electronic wavelength switching, the optimal operation parameters for a stationary and spectrally pure output at each of the three wavelengths 1064 nm, 1122 nm, and 1186 nm are investigated. Figure 2 shows the spectral output for different pump and seed configurations. For a maximum output power at 1064 nm, the pump power of the DC-YDFA was increased until the Raman threshold was reached (figure 2 a)). At a peak pulse power of 630 W, 97 % of the power was in the 1064 nm band (cf. fig. 2 d), blue trace). The spectral full width at half maximum (FWHM) was 38 pm. For 1122 nm operation, the 1064 nm pulses act as Raman pump and the 1122 nm seed laser as Raman probe. For maximum 1122 nm output power, we increased the 1064 nm pump power of the DC-YDFA until the onset of the next Raman order. For the Raman amplified 1122 nm light, we identify more than 90 % in-band power (cf. fig. 2 d), green trace) and a spectral FWHM of 47 pm. The total pulse peak power

was 830 W with 750 W within 0.5 nm around 1122 nm. When we further increased the pump power of the last amplifier, we would have expected the broadband Raman gain spectrum of fused silica arising around 1180 nm. However, we observed a spectrally narrowband line at 1186 nm with a linewidth of less than 70 pm (cf. fig. 2 c)). We determined a total pulse power of 1.15 kW with 900 W within ± 5 nm around the 1186 nm line. Furthermore, another narrowband component at 1257 nm is visible in the spectrum (cf. fig. 2 c)). It is worth noting that the intermediate wavelength, 1122 nm, is reduced by almost 20 dB compared to the 1186 nm peak in the spectrum.

Fig. 2. **a) – c)** Output spectra optimized for single wavelength operation and zoom in into linearized and normalized region around the center wavelength with spectral FWHM indicated. **d)** Integrated power over spectrum showing the high efficiency of the wavelength shifting process.

Usually, narrowband cascaded Raman shifting is obtained by either seeding with designated lasers or by employing fiber Bragg gratings (FBG) to form a resonator [5, 7]. In our case, we used none of the aforementioned. Instead, the narrowband output is generated by the system without any additional components. We believe that this narrowband line at 1186 nm is initially seeded by a FWM process involving the 1064 nm and 1122 nm photons. This FWM generated light later seeds the stimulated Raman process. An indicator for the FWM background is the equidistant frequency spacing of 14.5 THz of the three peaks (cf. fig. 2 a)). In contrast to SRS, FWM is a phase critical mechanism. Initial 1186 nm seed light will be generated by FWM over the coherence length $L_{coh} = \pi/\Delta k$. Δk is the phase mismatch, which can be estimated according to ref. [11] by $\Delta k = 2\pi\lambda D(\lambda)\Omega^2$, where $D(\lambda)$ is the material dispersion function, λ the wavelength and Ω the energy difference between the pump and signal wavelengths in wavenumber values. For $D(1186\text{nm})$ we used a value of

$D = 0.0056$ taken from [15], $\lambda=1186$ nm for the signal wavelength and $\Omega=483$ cm^{-1} as the energy difference. This results in a phase mismatch of ~ 97 m^{-1} . This indicates a coherence length of ~ 3.5 cm, meaning after only a few centimeters the newly FWM generated light would have a π phase shift and thus overall the 1186 nm light would be annihilated. Thus, according to the phase matching condition pure FWM is not enough to explain the observed 1186 nm. Our model is that the FWM signal light at 1186 nm is subsequently amplified by SRS. The SRS gain is sufficiently high to prevent complete back-conversion due to FWM light after the coherence length. It indicates, that the overlaid SRS effect in the glass fiber breaks the symmetry of the non-phase matched FWM generation. This finally leads to an efficient generation of narrowband light at 1186 nm. Our model of the FWM-assisted SRS mechanism is further supported by the observation of the onset of the third cascaded Raman Stokes order at 1257 nm, again narrowband and again at an optical frequency difference of exactly 14.5 THz (cf. fig. 2 c)).

Fig. 3. **a)** Combination of FWM and SRS in the fiber results in narrowband output at 1186 nm. **b)** Simulation of the output power for three spectral components 1064 nm, 1122 nm, and 1186 nm at varying 1064 nm input power and fixed 1122 nm seed.

To validate our theory, we simulated the observed generation of spectrally narrowband output of 1186 nm light with a model taking only the two mentioned effects -SRS and FWM- into account, to test whether this simple model can explain the observed behavior. The simulations are based on coupled amplitude equations for the three optical field components at 1064 nm, 1122 nm and 1186 nm, respectively [16]. In this model, the field components are assumed to be ideally monochromatic, and contributions beyond the 1st Raman-Stokes order are neglected. Our simulations do not contain any fitting parameters, i.e., all parameters are obtained from the material and fiber specifications, or calculated from the mode profile of the corresponding fiber. Figure 3 b) shows the simulated output power of the different spectral components after a fixed fiber configuration of 2 m Hi1060 and 2 m SMF28 fiber and a fixed input power of 5 mW at 1122 nm for a varied 1064 nm input power. We can see that the power levels match very well with our observations. Also, we can see that the pump fields are depleted almost entirely, as also reported by others [12]. It can be seen that the generation of the higher order cascaded Raman band at 1186 nm is directly influenced by the initial pump field at 1064 nm.

From the above mentioned observations and validated by the simulation, we found that the two key control mechanisms for the described wavelength shifting process are a) the launched 1064 nm power and b) applying 1122 nm seed or not. The shifting can be achieved at high dynamic speeds, as both applied light sources are semiconductor based and can be controlled on a few nanoseconds time scale, much faster than the time scale of Yb

doped gain material, which is on the order of milliseconds [17]. As an application of the wavelength shift mechanism and the rapidly controllable light sources, we show pulse-to-pulse wavelength switching between the three output wavelengths.

Fig. 4. Pulse-to-pulse wavelength switching with over 90 % efficiency by modulating pump and seed power. **a)** 1064 nm to 1122 nm. **b)** 1122 nm to 1186 nm. **c)** 1064 nm to 1186 nm. Left plots show 10 consecutive pulses. Right plots show zoom-in of the last two pulses with FWHM indicated.

Figure 4 shows time traces of pulse-to-pulse switching between the three different wavelengths at 50 kHz pulse repetition rate. The individual spectral components were separated with adequate long- and short-pass filters and recorded with a 500 MHz freespace photodiode connected to a 1 GHz realtime oscilloscope. For switching between 1064 nm and 1122 nm, the output power at 1064 nm was increased until the Raman threshold was reached. Then, the 1122 nm seed diode was turned on for every second pulse. As can be seen in figure 4 a), both spectral components achieve almost the same pulse peak power of ~ 600 W (calculated from cw-power). Figure 4 b) shows switching between 1122 nm and 1186 nm. To shift from 1122 nm to 1186 nm the initial 1064 nm peak was increased until 1186 nm pulses were optimized. Now, we reduced the initial 1064 nm seed power before the EOM for every second pulse by modulating the 1064 nm laser diode with a fast laser diode driver (WieserLabs, WL-LDC10D). We achieve a high extinction ration of 90 % between 1122 nm and 1186 nm. Finally, we present wavelength switching from 1064 nm to 1186 nm from pulse-to-pulse in figure 4 c). For this, we increased the 1064 nm seed diode modulation depth so that the lower energy pulses remained below the Raman threshold and switched on the 1122 nm seed only for the high energy pulses for 1186 nm generation. As there is a higher peak power necessary to generate 1186 nm light, the overall peak power is higher for that component than for the 1064 nm pulses. While the 1064 nm pulses have less than 1 % out-of-band power, there is about 10 % power at shorter wavelength remaining for the 1186 nm pulses. This shows that the shifting process is overall

very efficient (cf. time traces in fig. 4 and the spectra in fig. 2). In both figures, it can be seen that the pump beam gets depleted almost entirely. This is in agreement with predicted and observed values reported in literature [12].

In conclusion, we reported on a highly efficient and spectrally narrowband cascaded Raman shifter, where the spectral linewidth is much lower than what is expected by the Raman gain bandwidth. The narrowing is attributed to a FWM seeded Raman shifting process. This is in concordance with simulated results where the model includes only FWM and Raman amplification to confirm qualitatively the observed behavior. We demonstrate rapid switching between the three output wavelengths out of the same single-mode fiber at 50 kHz switching rate which could be increased to the MHz rate. The resulting pulses at the longer wavelength have the same time characteristics as the pump pulse and the spectral characteristics of the seed laser. The wavelengths at 1064 nm and 1122 nm were already used for TICO-SRS (time-encoded stimulated Raman) – microscopy and – spectroscopy [3, 18] and TPEF (two-photon excited fluorescence) imaging [4, 19]. Together with the new narrowband high power output at 1186 nm, this can extend the spectral coverage of single wavelength fiber lasers [4, 19, 20] in biomedical imaging. Furthermore, the high dynamic capability of the pulse-to-pulse switching approach can enable high speed multi-wavelength applications in spectroscopy and nonlinear microscopic imaging.

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